
THE USE OF COMPUTER-BASED LEARNING ASSESSMENT FOR PROFESSIONAL COURSES: A STRATEGY TO IMPROVED STUDENTS' SCHOLASTIC PERFORMANCE

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ABSTRACT

Background/Objectives: While the increase in classroom technology, it is necessary to examine how assessment is administered through technology. The purpose of this study is to understand how students and faculty are perceived and examine the effectiveness of the computer-based assessment in professional education courses (Educational Technology) at Northern Iloilo Polytechnic State College, Iloilo, Philippines. **Methods:** The research design utilized in this study is mixed-method research. A computer-based assessment was utilized to assess students' performance in educational technology. This instrument was validated, and pilot tested to establish reliability. Each campus of NIPSC selected ten students of 70 as respondents during Academic Year 2016-2017. Frequency count, mean, standard deviation, and Wilcoxon signed-rank test were statistical tools used for data analyses. **Findings:** The study's finding showed a high score of students in the posttest ensured better performance of the students in educational technology. The increase in the posttest per performance level of the students was due to an accurate measure of what they have learned in educational technology. The majority of students users agreed that online assessment was faster than the paper and pencil form. Also, users agreed that online assessment is contemporary and more systematic. They also stated that online assessment is consistent with the teaching style, but they are less anxious. Furthermore, according to faculty and students, ninety percent (90%) believed that computer-based assessment accurately measures what they are teaching and what they learned in school, respectively. **Novelty:** With the current situation that the education system is in new normal, computer-based learning is important in flexible learning. And assessment using technology is a great help to both faculty and students. Thus, state universities and colleges (SUCs) should adopt this innovation to help teaching and learning.

Key words: Tertiary Level, Teacher Education, Professional Courses, Computer-Based Assessment, Improved Performance.

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1. INTRODUCTION

The lack of motivation among students during their developmental and educational improvement correlates with difficulty in life. Regardless of the attitudes and behaviors of students inside the classroom, all of them have talents and potentials ⁽¹⁾. Thus, teachers are always considered role models and inspirations among students. Teaching is a noble profession. Notwithstanding problems teachers experienced, the majority strive hard to give quality and equity education to all learners. Teaching today is a far more complex profession than a couple of decades ago. The enthusiastically shifting pace of development in science and technology has brought about corresponding changes in the way we view teaching. Thus, while earlier on, we have always been content with testing and measuring students' cognitive skills through teacher-made tests, today, we test and measure cognitive development and the affective, psychomotor development of the learners. Therefore, the teacher is expected to be fully conversant of the measurement and assessment procedures that underpin testing in the three domains: cognitive, affective, and psychomotor domains ⁽²⁾.

Assessment is a dimension of the information acquired to gauge the next level in the educational process. Assessment is an essential division in learning. An effective assessment system is linked to adequate quality and quantity evidence to enhance students learning processes and performance ⁽³⁾. One of the major advancements in tests and measurement is the recognition of the inadequacies inherent in outmoded cognitive testing through pencil and paper tests. Indeed, skills, abilities, and competencies could not be successfully assessed if one uses traditional measurement processes. An assessment covering such techniques as portfolio assessment, rating scales, self-reports, and others, offers an alternative to outdated test and measurement techniques. While the procedure is not yet used extensively in educational systems worldwide, its potential for enhancing the teaching-learning process is now widely recognized ⁽⁴⁾⁽⁵⁾.

A dispute is made for less research on reliability and summative self-assessment and more on formative self-assessment's cognitive and affective mechanisms. The review showed self-assessment as to the most beneficial for achievement and self-regulated learning. This is also a process to deepen learning and enhance learners' performances by properly utilized and reinforced by training ⁽⁶⁾.

In recent times, machinery has played an essential role in society. All governments worldwide directive the increase in the use of technology. Computer-based technology is an influence that inspires students' academic engagement. The usage of technology motivated learners to be at school and could improve academic performance. But many teachers don't utilize computers effectively. Studies revealed only very few teachers routinely used computers for instructional purposes. Computers are not used across the curriculum ⁽⁷⁾.

Lately, schools have shifted to technology as a mode of teaching and learning ⁽⁸⁾. Communication and computer technologies are being widespread and used for all purposes. Thus, Information and Communications Technology (ICT) are utilized in higher education ⁽⁹⁾. The integration of ICT in the teaching-learning process enhances teachers' instructional materials and scholastic performance among learners ⁽¹⁰⁾. ICT is now part of tertiary learners' evaluation and electronic learning like the computer-Based Assessment or CBA. CBA is an

essential tool to evaluate students' performance ⁽⁹⁾. There are many advantages of CBA in learning. The students can immediately access the grades and feedback. They can also have flexibility in time on taking the exams. The teachers can escape from personal interpretation and legibility ⁽¹¹⁾.

While Computer-based Testing (CBT) is dubbed as the most innovative approach in assessment by various states in the US, with the development of CBT, experts applauded as cheaper, speedier test delivery and accessibility for students with disabilities ⁽¹²⁾. CBT is an alternative for pencil and paper tests. For instance, the common type of assessment in the medical field is paper and pencil format. But with, the use of technology-based assessment was viable for remote and does not require administration by health practitioners ⁽¹³⁾.

Often associated with leakage, the out-of-date assessment methods are having issues like human errors and recording. The paper-based assessment was improved with the use of technologies and connectivity. This evaluation tool is called Web-based assessment, serves as the answer for the education system evaluation, and promotes distance learning ⁽¹⁴⁾.

Online education endures rising in many colleges and universities around the world. The study results about online courses and students' engagement revealed a significant relationship. Students taking more online classes posed quantitative reasoning. But interactions among peers and teachers were lessened; thus, higher institutions adopting e-learning should consider some factors to make students work a variety of delivery types ⁽¹⁵⁾. The information and communication technologies (ICT) tools are the key element in this time of the pandemic. Digital teacher competence and teacher education opportunities to learn digital competence are crucial to implementing flexible learning ⁽¹⁶⁾.

The assessment of problem-solving competence is a vital topic in learning and instruction vocational and tertiary levels. It would be easy to understand the complexity and authenticity of the problem-solving ability with the approach. But the study suggests furthering systematized and automated innovation ⁽¹⁷⁾. This study attempts to assess, evaluate, and develop the recent students' learning outcomes of Professional Education subjects, specifically in Educational Technology at Northern Iloilo Polytechnic State College (NIPSC Systems) Teacher Education program.

2. METHODS

2.1. Research Design

The research design utilized in this study is the mixed method of research. In this study, the researcher would like to find out the perceptions of students and faculty on the new assessment methods, which is the computer-based assessment, by giving pretest and posttest of the newly constructed test questions based on the LET reviewer in an educational technology subject.

2.2. Respondents of the Study

The respondents of this study were the six campuses of Northern Iloilo Polytechnic State College (NIPSC), offering teacher education programs. On each campus, ten respondents were identified. The total respondents were seventy (70).

2.3. Research Instrument

This research utilized the existing assessment learning test, and the researcher made a computer-based assessment test in educational technology duly validated and trial-tested to establish reliability. The assessment was taken from the textbook and Licensure Examination for Teachers (LET) reviewer on educational technology. The researcher constructed a matrix of activities to test the computer-based method to come up with a scheme to be followed during

the duration of the research. The researcher constructed seventy (70) items test questions based on the learning content of the educational technology OBE syllabus made by the researcher and duly approved by the Dean of Education and Dean of Instruction NIPSC System. The researcher submitted this item to a panel of experts for content and face validation. To determine the description score, the researcher adopted the description of a five (5) point grading scale.

2.4. Data Gathering Procedure

The researcher-made test was the tool for pretest and posttest. The results served as the tool in determining the impact of educational technology on the use of computer-based learning assessment of the learners. The researcher orients the respondents on rules and policies by using the computer, nature, and mechanics on how to answer the test and feedback and comments. The posttest is to conduct after a week of the pretest.

2.5. Data Analyses

The test instrument was administered. The data were gathered, organized, computed, and tabulated. The Statistical Package of the Social Sciences (SPSS) software was used for statistical analysis. Statistical tools were the means and assigned scales, standard deviation, and Wilcoxon signed-rank test. The differences were tested at 0.05 alpha.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Table 1 shows the pretest and posttest professional education performance of the students using the computer-based assessment.

Table 1. Pretest and Posttest Professional Education (Ed. Tech.) Performance of the students in computer-based Learning Assessment

Category		SD	Mean	Description
Main Campus	Pretest	7.03	36.60	Satisfactory
	Posttest	5.19	40.30	Satisfactory
Batad Campus	Pretest	2.58	41.70	Very Satisfactory
	Posttest	2.49	42.70	Very Satisfactory
Concepcion Campus	Pretest	9.73	37.80	Satisfactory
	Posttest	1.16	42.30	Very Satisfactory
Lemery Campus	Pretest	6.82	38.70	Satisfactory
	Posttest	1.83	42.30	Very Satisfactory
Ajuy Campus	Pretest	5.90	38.80	Satisfactory
	Posttest	2.91	40.70	Satisfactory
Barotac Viejo campus	Pretest	2.67	37.40	Satisfactory
	Posttest	2.67	27.40	Satisfactory
Total	Pretest	6.19	38.83	Satisfactory
	Posttest	3.39	41.00	Satisfactory

Legend: 55.01 – 70.00 (*Excellent*); 41.01 – 55.00 (*Very Satisfactory*); 27.01 – 41.00 (*Satisfactory*); 13.01 – 27.00 (*Poor*); and, 0 – 13.00 (*Very Poor*).

The pretest in Main Campus in educational technology performance of students using the computer-based assessment was "Satisfactory" (M=36.60, SD= 7.03). At the same time, the posttest results also show the same as the pretest, which is "Satisfactory" (M= 40.30, SD= 5.19). These results imply that the students' knowledge in educational technology is satisfactorily sufficient, and they feel more comfortable using the CBA.

In Batad Campus, students' pretest educational technology performance using the computer-based assessment was "Very Satisfactory" (M= 41.70, SD= 2.58). At the same time, the posttest

results also show similar to the pretest, which is "Satisfactory" also (M= 42.70, SD= 2.49). These results imply that pretest and posttest are almost identical. The slight increase in the standard deviation of the posttest means the scores of the students clustered around the mean. In other words, the students are more comfortable using the CBA.

In addition, the pretest educational technology performance of the students in Concepcion Campus using the computer-based assessment was "Satisfactory" (M=37.80, SD= 9.73). This result implies that the student's knowledge of educational technology was sufficient. In other words, the student's understanding of educational technology was basic, and they were slightly confused using the CBA. During the posttest, the educational technology performance of the students remarkably increased and was described as "Very Satisfactory" (M=42.30, SD=1.16). These results reveal that the student has gained more understanding and feels comfortable in educational technology using the computer-based assessment. The slight increase in the standard deviation means that scores of the students cluster around the mean.

Lemery Campus revealed the pretest educational technology performance of the students using the computer-based assessment was "Satisfactory" (M=37.80, SD=6.83). This result implies that the student's knowledge of educational technology was sufficient. In other words, the student's knowledge of educational technology was basic, and they were slightly confused using the CBA. During the posttest, the educational technology performance of the students remarkably increased and was described as "Very Satisfactory" (M=42.30, SD=1.83). These results reveal that the students feel comfortable using the computer-based assessment. The slight increase in the standard deviation means that the scores of the students cluster around the mean.

In Ajuy Campus, the pretest in professional education performance of students using the computer-based assessment was "Satisfactory" (M=38.80, SD=5.90) while the posttest is also "Satisfactory" (M=40.70, SD=2.91). This result implies that the student's knowledge was adequate. Their prior knowledge of the subject was very satisfactory. The pretest in Barotac Viejo Campus in professional education performance of students using the computer-based assessment when group according to campus was "Satisfactory" (M=37.40, SD=2.67). At the same time, the posttest results also show similar to the pretest, which is "Satisfactory" (M=27.40, SD=2.67). This result implies that the pretest and posttest are almost similar. The slight increase in the standard deviation of the posttest means the scores of the students clustered around the mean.

The findings showed a description of "Satisfactory" with a mean of 3 8.83 and an SD of 6.19. The present study has demonstrated that such concerns are groundless-students not only maintained their cognitive gains as they had the opportunity to research and perform a task that benefits the development of scientific reasoning. Such an opportunity would never have been offered by paper and pencil-based assessment since technology offer now a day's an easy way of learning for students. This result implies that the students' knowledge in Professional Education (Educational Technology) was sufficient. In other words, the student's knowledge in Educational Technology subject was sufficient. During the posttest, the Professional Education (Ed. Tech.) performance of the students remarkably increased and was described as "Very Satisfactory" (M = 41.0, SD = 3.39).

These results reveal that the students have gained more understanding and comfortable in using the computer-based assessment. The slight decrease in the standard deviation means that the scores of the students cluster around the mean. Many students believe that e-learning has great potential in higher education ⁽¹⁸⁾. Many colleges and universities advocate online education because studies have proved it help learners quantitative reasoning skills. But students with greater exposure to online learning reported having less exposure to teaching practices and interaction among peers ⁽¹⁹⁾.

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Table 1 shows the Wilcoxon signed test results of this study.

Table 2 Wilcoxon Signed Ranks Test

Category		Asymp. Sig (2 tailed)
Main Campus	Pretest	.317
	Posttest	
Batad Campus	Pretest	.317
	Posttest	
Concepcion Campus	Pretest	.317
	Posttest	
Lemery Campus	Pretest	.317
	Posttest	
Ajuy Campus	Pretest	.317
	Posttest	
Barotac Viejo Campus	Pretest	.317
	Posttest	

There was no significant difference in the pretest, and posttest per campus in professional Education (Ed. Tech.) performance mean scores of the students in CBA Asymp. Sig. (2 tailed) (59) = .317, $p < .05$. The null hypothesis, which states that there is no significant difference in students' performance using a CBA at Northern Iloilo Polytechnic State College when grouped according to campus, is accepted. The increase in the scores of the students in CBA can be attributed to the technology being used during the assessment. The results revealed a significant difference between the pretest and posttest scores showing a remarkable improvement in the students' IT achievement using the traditional assessment method (paper and pencil based). Many of the students improved their scores by 30% or more. In addition, the researchers were able to observe the students' behavior, both traditional and CBA. The researcher further noted that the students' appeared to be more engaged on any online assessment. The researcher concluded that at-risk students who benefited from the traditional assessment improved their test scores from previous assessments using CBA.

Assessment of learning processes is an essential part of the educational practice to evaluate the students' knowledge, skills, and attitudes. New computer-based tool design brings about the success of e-learning ⁽¹¹⁾. CBA is effective if it's playful to learners; it's easy to use and useful ⁽¹⁰⁾. Thus, the effectiveness of CBA depends on the acceptance of learners ⁽²⁰⁾.

Table 3 shows the feedback of the students on the CBA in professional education Courses (Ed. Tech.).

Table 3. Feedbacks of students from 7 campuses on the CBA in professional education courses (Ed. Tech.)

Campus	Respondent Number	Responses
Main Campus	Student 1	Taking the CBA in educational technology five (5) times in a year stated he is more comfortable when taking CBA than the traditional one.
	Student 2	He spends less time doing CBA. It makes examination writing easier for him.
	Student 3	The marking is more accurate because computers don't suffer from human error, and he is confident that his grades for CBA are secure. Students' general opinions about the online assessment tool: most users agreed that online assessment was faster than the paper and pencil form. On average, the users agreed that online assessment is contemporary and more systematic.

		All the users think this kind of online assessment is consistent with the teaching style, but there is little disagreement that they are less anxious.
Batad Campus	Student 3	An online test environment is appropriate for test-taking and convenient. The information is easily modified and understood by students in educational technology.
	Student 4	Marking is more accurate because computers don't suffer from human error. He is confident that his grades for online assessments are secured.
Concepcion Campus		The assessment is easy because of multiple choice; it's all relevant to content areas and user-friendly. CBA favors those who have a personal computer. The data collected from the computer-based assessment is clear and easy to understand and use.
Lemery Campus	Students 1, 2, and 3	They prefer writing all examinations online CBA is a more modern approach than the traditional one (paper and pencil).
	Student 4	He finds it hard to concentrate on the computer-based assessment questions.
	Student 5	After taking the CBA, he is more comfortable, spending less time, and confident that his grades for online assessment are secured.
	Students 6 and 7	They are comfortable after taking CBA because immediately they know their scores and grades.
Ajuy Campus	Student 1	He prefers to take all the online examination CBA in the mid-term and final exam during the semester on multiple choice. He added that using a computer makes examination taking easier.
	Students 2, 3, and 4	They find it hard to concentrate on the questions when doing CBA exams. They can guess the questions; online multiple-choice questions don't reflect their level of knowledge.
	Student 5	The information is easily modified and understood by students in educational technology. The data collected from the computer-based assessment are clear and easy to understand and use.
	Student 6	Web navigation should be allowed during the computer-based assessment.
	Student 7	Stresses him because of time pressure.
Barotac Viejo Campus	Student 1	Preferred CBA than the traditional approach. Less time spent in CBA
	Students 2 and 3	The type of questions available (Multiple choice, true/false, etc.) fit the needs of the content area. Marking is more accurate because computers don't suffer human error. It saves school/college money, manpower's time, and energy.
	Student 4	The assessment program being used shares results with the grading program easily. The information is easily modified and understood by students in educational technology.
	Student 5	Reacts that, he is more confident that his grades for online assessments are secured. Also, computer-based assessment is relevant to all content areas.
	Student 6	CBA favors those students who have their personal computers. He can log in anywhere in his comfortable mood.
	Student 7	Results are shared online, and assessments are secured.

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Furthermore, with millions of learners affected by the pandemic, online movement in the history of education was pushed. Universities and colleges worldwide were recommended for information communication experts for online distance learning applications. With proper implementation, the adaption of e-learning could lead to an increase in learners population, cheaper, and increase in revenue for schools ⁽²¹⁾.

The development of computer-based test (CBT) Models Based on the web makes it easier for users to use it and supervisors to accomplish questions ⁽²²⁾.

Table 4 shows the faculty perceptions on the CBA in professional courses of 7 campuses of NIPSC.

Table 4 Faculty perceptions on the CBA in professional education courses at NIPSC

Campus	Responses
Main Campus	The computer-based assessment saves time by eliminating the need to make paper copies and have instant feedback given by the students. The time spent correcting papers is eliminated. With the program being used, there is a question bank where you can potentially store thousands of questions and change them in and out with the click of a mouse.
Batad Campus	This type of assessment is more dependable in a traditional Way because most problem questions come from paper and pencil tests. They add that CBA is the direction that education is heading; it is up to educators to push the envelope and strive to challenge students and provide them with the experience they need to succeed.
Concepcion Campus	The computer-based assessment accurately measures what they are teaching in class. With the program being used, there is a question bank where you can potentially store thousands of questions and change them in and out with the click of a mouse.
Lemery Campus	It can determine the impact that this type of assessment has on education and results. They believe that computer-based assessments accurately measure what they are teaching in class. Faculty two (2) says cheating is inevitable in this assessment method.
Ajuy Campus	The faculty suggested, Web navigation should be allowed during the computer-based assessment; computer-based testing would be improved by allowing students to complete it from home. They add CBA saves time and be given at home.
Barotac Viejo Campus	The computer-based assessment on educational technology improves assessment scores; it accurately measures what they have taught. Computer-based assessments are easier to complete than traditional paper-based assessments; CBA fairly measures what is learned i.e., spelling errors, incomplete responses, etc.

The CBAs are not affordable to administer high-stakes examinations in regular schools. Current evidence showed even European countries that CBAs are not yet in teachers' toolboxes. Also, the adoption of CBAs is low ⁽²³⁾. The review computer-based assessment for learning (CBAfL) in elementary and secondary education displayed great possibilities for science learning measurement technology innovations ⁽²⁴⁾.

Finally, most of the professors at the NIPSC system believe that computer-based assessment accurately measures what they are teaching in class. It saves time, money, and effort. The availability of technology and facilities is crucial in integrating online education ⁽²⁵⁾. During the COVID-19 pandemic, schools worldwide shifted to online teaching and learning. Face-to-face

instructions cannot take place for a longer time; thus, governments should identify the policies to maximize the effectiveness of online learning. Also, parents and teachers are fundamental instruments to help students' attitudes towards flexible learning. Policy focus on digital learning should be the main priority of national governments ⁽²⁶⁾. NIPSC's quest for university hood, facilities, and equipment are the college's top priorities.

4. CONCLUSIONS

The high mean scores of students in the posttest ensured better performance of the students. The increase in the posttest performance level of the students was due to an accurate measure of they have learned. The computer-based assessment was more dependable in a traditional way because most problem questions come from paper and pencil tests. Students are looking towards the future when it comes to assessment. Approximately ninety percent (90%) feel comfortable with logging in and taking an assessment on the computer compared to the approximately ninety percent (90%) of the faculty who think it is a simple task. Both faculty and students agree the opportunity is there to be able to take advantage of the resources that are available to us. Students do not have a problem using a computer to take the test. Most feel that it is easier to take a test on the computer, whereas only ninety percent (90%) of faculty thought it was easier. Students are moving along at a much faster rate than many teachers. Educators tend to get stuck in their ways and do not necessarily resist change but are not the quickest to embrace it. Students can tell you how they learn and what they believe is the best way to be assessed on what is being taught in class. Ninety percent (90%) of students felt that computer-based assessment accurately measures what they have learned in class; compared to the ninety percent (90%) of teachers who feel the same way, there is not a tremendous gap to bridge. Students believed that their grades were positively impacted by using technology to assess their learning. Teachers believe that this is the direction of education; it is up to educators to push the envelope and strive to challenge students and provide them with the experience they need to succeed.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The professional education courses professors at Northern Iloilo Polytechnic State College system teaching educational technology 1 and 2 should adopt computer-based assessments to assess student performance. Professional education professors who are comfortable with the use of paper and pencil-based tests should try to study and shift to computer-based assessment to improve students' performance. The Dean of Instruction should conduct an in-service training workshop for professional education professors to orient them to new assessment methods and other teaching approaches. The Vice President for Academic Affairs should evaluate the effectiveness of professors teaching professional education subjects in education and other courses. Moreover, the administration should send professors to seminars in assessment to upgrade their competence in teaching the subject. This researcher recommends that further research is needed to determine how students' perceive the extent of the impact that computer-based assessment has on student learning. A study that examines assessment scores as compared to paper-based scores should be completed on a larger scale to determine whether there is a positive impact on student performance or not. Similar studies involving students in other courses are strongly recommended to validate the findings of this study.

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